

The Church of St. George, Kalamiou (Selino), Crete

By Nicolyna Enriquez, University of California, Los Angeles

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The church of St. George in the middle of the village of Kalamiou in the province of Selino is a single nave chapel with a pointed barrel vault interior and saddle roof exterior. The interior is divided into two bays by a transverse arch. The sanctuary apse has an image of the Virgin Platytera above the images of four co-officiating bishops: St. Nicholas, St. John Chrysostom, St. Basil and an unidentified bishop. The triumphal arch shows the Hospitality of Abraham (top register) and the Annunciation (middle register). Two deacon saints, presumably St. Stephen on the left and St. Romanus on the right, flank the apse. The northern wall of the sanctuary has the image of St. George on horseback next to an unidentified bishop saint. St. Cyril of Alexandria is the only saint still visible on the southern wall of the sanctuary. The barrel vault of the sanctuary shows three scenes from the Christological cycle including the Ascension, the Anastasis and the Nativity. Two additional scenes can no longer be identified. The nave includes additional scenes from the Christological cycle, including the Crucifixion, the Baptism of Christ, and the Raising of Lazarus, and from the Life of the Virgin, including the Visitation and the Virgin blessed by the three Priests. The gallery of saints along the southern wall of the nave includes St. Nicholas, the Archangel Michael, St. Kyriaki and another military saint. The northern wall shows St. Theodore and St. Demetrios both on horseback next to St. Paraskevi. The western wall is mostly whitewashed although the door is flanked by two female saints. The dedicatory inscription is located on the left side of the entrance. Although only partially preserved it notes that the church was originally dedicated to the Mother of God (Panagia) and was sponsored by Tziskos, Antonios, Michael, Ioannis, and Leon Examodis. The church was finished on Thursday 18 May in the Byzantine year 6949 (1441) and painted by the priest Georgios Partzalis.

Date Range: 1441 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Village of Kalamiou (Selino), Crete

Region tags: Crete, Greece

The church is located in the village of Kalamiou in the province of Selino on the island of Crete.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See p. 193-4 (no. 63).

– Source 2: Gerola, Giuseppe, and K. Lassithiotakis. Τοπογραφικός κατάλογος των τοιχογραφημένων εκκλησιών της Κρήτης. Edited by K. Lassithiotakis. Heraklion: Εταιρίας Κρητικών Ιστορικών Μελετών, 1961. See no. 94.

– Source 3: Gerola, Giuseppe. Monumenti Veneti nell'isola di Creta. 4 vols. Venice: R. Istituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. See Vol. II, 309, and IV, 437-38, no. 9.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Single nave chapel with a pointed barrel vault interior and saddle roof exterior.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: Worship and burial.

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to St. George.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: According to the dedicatory inscription the church was sponsored by Tziskos, Antonios, Michael, Ioannis, and Leon Examodis and painted by the priest Georgios Partzalis.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Plaster and stone.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

- ↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
 - Yes
- ↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
 - No
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - Yes

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Church of St. George, Kalamiou (Selino), Crete, Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. p.193-194, no. 63.

Reference: The Church of St. George, Kalamiou (Selino), Crete, Gerola, Giuseppe, and K. Lassithiotakis. Τοπογραφικός Κατάλογος Των Τοιχογραφημένων Εκκλησιών Της Κρήτης. Heraklion: Εταιρίας Κρητικών Ιστορικών Μελετών, 1961. p.no. 94

Reference: The Church of St. George, Kalamiou (Selino), Crete, Gerola, Giuseppe. Monumenti Veneti Nell'isola Di Creta. Venice: R. Istituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. p.Vol. II, 309; IV, 437-38, no. 9.